

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND RESEARCH IN ODISHA

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INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic represented an unprecedented challenge for researchers all over the world. In Odisha, the pandemic has disrupted the research landscape in multiple ways, with research in healthcare, social sciences, and economics becoming crucial in the fight against the pandemic. This viewpoint summarises the research work done in Odisha during the COVID-19 pandemic and how it affected the state's reaction to the epidemic.

RESEARCH IN HEALTHCARE

In Odisha, the pandemic has underscored the need for strengthening healthcare systems, including better preparedness for public health emergencies. Researchers in the state have played a critical role in studying the pandemic's epidemiology and understanding its impact on health outcomes. Several studies have focused on COVID-19's transmission dynamics, clinical presentations, and mortality rates in different populations. One study conducted in Odisha aimed to investigate the transmission dynamics of COVID-19 in a community setting. The study found that social distancing and mask-wearing successfully decreased the spread of COVID-19.^[1] Seroprevalence studies were carried out throughout the state at various times and in various populations, which helped in a better understanding of the spread of the disease with time and also about the immunodynamics.^[2,3] Mental Health was one of the key focus areas during the pandemic; few studied its impact as far as suicide is concerned and found a higher rate than before.^[4] Studies were also undertaken to study the effects of COVID-19 vaccines in eliciting an immune response by various researchers, and their findings reported good immunogenicity of the vaccines.^[5,6]

RESEARCH IN SOCIAL SCIENCES

The COVID-19 pandemic has also significantly impacted society, including its economic and social consequences. Researchers in Odisha have studied the pandemic's impact on vulnerable populations, such as migrant workers, women, and children. They have also explored the effectiveness of various government policies and interventions to mitigate the pandemic's impact. One study conducted in Odisha aimed to understand the effects of the pandemic on migrant workers. The study found that the pandemic severely impacted migrant workers' livelihoods, with many losing

jobs and facing significant economic hardships. The study also examined the effectiveness of government cash transfer programs in mitigating the pandemic's economic impact on vulnerable populations. The study found that cash transfer programs effectively financially supported vulnerable households during the pandemic.^[7]

CONCLUSION

The COVID-19 pandemic represented unprecedented challenges for researchers across the globe, and Odisha is no exception, with research in healthcare, social sciences, and economics becoming crucial in the fight against the pandemic. Researchers in the state have played a critical role in understanding the pandemic's epidemiology and impact on health outcomes. They have also explored the pandemic's impact on vulnerable populations and the effectiveness of various government policies and interventions to mitigate its impact on society.

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